

Kinetics and mechanism of chromium(III)-catalysed oxidation of ethane-1,2-diol and propane-1,2-diol by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulfuric acid media

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Manuscript received 5 August 1999, accepted 31 December 1999

The kinetics and mechanism of chromium(III)-catalysed oxidation of the title diols by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulfuric acid media to their corresponding aldehydes through the C-C bond cleavage (i.e. glycol splitting) under the conditions, $[\text{diol}]_T \gg [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_T \gg [\text{Cr}]_T$ at different temperatures (35–50°) have been studied. In 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sulfuric acid media, the experimentally observed rate law conforms to

$$-d \ln [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] / dt = k_{\text{obs}} = a[\text{diol}]_T[\text{Cr}]_T / (b + c[\text{Cr}]_T)$$

where, $[\text{diol}]_T$ and $[\text{Cr}]_T$ give the total concentrations of the substrate and catalyst, respectively; a , b and c are constants at a particular temperature and fixed $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$. The process has been found acid-catalysed. From the hydrogen sulfate dependence, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ has been identified as the kinetically active species. The proposed mechanism involves the formation of an intermediate involving the oxidant, catalyst and substrate, and a $\text{Cr}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cr}^{\text{IV}}$ catalytic cycle has been suggested to operate.

In continuation of our studies¹ on metal ion catalysis in Ce^{IV} oxidation of different substrates in different acid media, we present here the mechanistic aspects of the title reactions in which the substrates experience the C-C bond cleavage (i.e. glycol splitting). In fact, very few systems on Cr^{III} catalysis in Ce^{IV} oxidation have been studied^{1c,2} and their mechanistic aspects differ significantly for different substrates. Our preliminary observations indicate that in the absence of any catalyst, Ce^{IV} oxidation of the title substrates in aqueous H_2SO_4 media is kinetically sluggish. In the presence of Cr^{III} process becomes fairly fast and the rate is quite measurable by the titrimetric quenching technique.

Results and Discussion

Dependence on $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$: The rate of disappearance of Ce^{IV} shows a first order dependence on $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ up to ~80–85%, then the plot of $\log [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_t$ vs t slightly deviates in some cases. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) are independent of the initial concentration of Ce^{IV} in the 2–4.5 $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ range,

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] / dt = k[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}], \text{ or } -d \ln[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] / dt = k_{\text{obs}} \quad (1)$$

Dependence on $[\text{substrate}]_T$: At fixed $[\text{Cr}]_T$, k_{obs} shows a strictly first order dependence on $[\text{diol}]_T$ in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sulfuric acid media,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_s[\text{diol}]_T \quad (2)$$

In 1.0 mol dm⁻³ H_2SO_4 , the values of $10^3 k_s$ (dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹) are : 3.02 \pm 0.17 (40°, $[\text{Cr}]_T = 0.03$ mol dm⁻³), 4.11 \pm 0.20 (45°, $[\text{Cr}]_T = 0.02$ mol dm⁻³), 3.06 \pm 0.12 (50°, $[\text{Cr}]_T =$

0.0025 mol dm⁻³) for ethane-1,2-diol; 10.80 \pm 0.20 (35°, $[\text{Cr}]_T = 0.08$ mol dm⁻³), 15.16 \pm 0.25 (40°, $[\text{Cr}]_T = 0.08$ mol dm⁻³), 18.33 \pm 0.35 (45°, $[\text{Cr}]_T = 0.05$ mol dm⁻³) for propane-1,2-diol.

Dependence on $[\text{Cr}]_T$: In the absence of Cr^{III} , the reactions practically do not proceed (less than 5%) under the present kinetic conditions. This is why in evaluating the k_{obs} no correction for the uncatalysed path was taken into consideration.

The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) at fixed $[\text{diol}]_T$ increases sharply (Fig. 1) with the increase of $[\text{Cr}]_T$ (= total concentration of chromium added as catalyst). Thus from the experimental fit, the dependence on $[\text{substrate}]_T$ and $[\text{catalyst}]_T$ can be expressed as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a[\text{Cr}]_T[\text{diol}]_T / (b + c[\text{Cr}]_T) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or } 1/k_{\text{obs}} = \{b/(a[\text{diol}]_T, [\text{Cr}]_T)\} + \{c/(a[\text{diol}]_T)\} \quad (4)$$

In 1.0 mol dm⁻³ H_2SO_4 , a , b and c are constants and expressed in terms of different rate constants. The constants are estimated from the linear plots ($r > 0.988$) of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Cr}]_T$ (cf. eqn. 4).

Dependence on $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$: For variations in $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ over the 0.55–1.75 mol dm⁻³ range at fixed $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{diol}]_T$ and $[\text{Cr}]_T$, the composition of the mixture, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] + [\text{HClO}_4] \approx [\text{H}^+] = 1.75$ mol dm⁻³ was varied³. This leads to $[\text{HSO}_4^-] \approx [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$. Here $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ shows a rate-retarding effect. The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ are linear ($r > 0.986$) with posi-

Fig. 1. Effect of $[Cr]_T$ on k_{obs} for the Cr^{III} -catalysed oxidation of propane-1,2-diol by Ce^{IV} in aqueous H_2SO_4 media. (A) 35° , (B) 40° , (C) 45° , $[Ce^{IV}]_T = (2.5-4.5) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[propane-1,2-diol]_T = 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Na^+] + [K^+] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

tive intercepts (Fig. 2). The $[HSO_4^-]$ dependence is expressed from the experimental fit in the following form,

$$k_{obs} = ml / \{n + p[HSO_4^-]\} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or, } 1/k_{obs} = (n/m) + (p/m) [HSO_4^-] \quad (6)$$

Dependence on $[H^+]$: For variations in $[H^+]$ over the $0.375-1.75 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ range at fixed $[HSO_4^-]$, the composition of the mixture, $[HSO_4^-] + [NaHSO_4] \approx [HSO_4^-] = 1.75 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was varied³ assuming $[H^+] \approx [HSO_4^-]$. Under the

Fig. 2. Effect of $[HSO_4^-]$ on k_{obs} for the Cr^{III} -catalysed oxidation of ethane-1,2-diol by Ce^{IV} in aqueous H_2SO_4 media. $[Ce^{IV}]_T = 4.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[ethane-1,2-diol]_T = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cr]_T = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Na^+] + [K^+] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] + [HClO_4] = [H^+] = 1.75 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $temp = 45^\circ$

conditions, for ethane-1,2-diol: $[Ce^{IV}]_T = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cr]_T = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Na^+] + [K^+] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[ethane-1,2-diol]_T = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 45° , for $[H^+] = 0.38, 0.55, 0.85, 1.20, 1.50$ and 1.75 mol dm^{-3} , the corresponding $10^4 k_{obs}$ values are 3.6, 4.3, 5.8, 8.2, 9.8 and 12.3 s^{-1} ; for propane-1,2-diol: $[Ce^{IV}]_T = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cr]_T = 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Na^+] + [K^+] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[propane-1,2-diol]_T = 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 40° , for $[H^+] = 0.70, 0.80, 1.0, 1.2, 1.5$ and 1.75 mol dm^{-3} , the corresponding $10^4 k_{obs}$ values are 2.42, 2.78, 3.20, 4.80, 5.91 and 6.68 s^{-1} .

Because of the existence of so many proton dependent equilibria (e.g. SO_4^{2-}/HSO_4^- , $Ce^{IV}-HSO_4^-/SO_4^{2-}/H^+$, Ce^{IV} -substrate/ H^+ etc.) among the reactants, the quantitative interpretation of $[H^+]$ dependence is very much complicated and uncertain. Because of this complexity in the present system, no attempt was made to explain the observed $[H^+]$ dependence^{6,7} from the proposed scheme. However, the qualitative observation is in agreement with the fact that the Ce^{IV} oxidation reactions in aqueous H_2SO_4 media are acid-catalysed⁵. On protonation, positive charge on the Ce^{IV} -sulfato species increases and it facilitates the electron transfer towards the Ce^{IV} centre. It may be one of the contributing factors⁵ for the observed acid-catalysis in the present system.

Acrylonitrile polymerization test: Cr^{III} alone cannot initiate polymerization of acrylonitrile under the experimental conditions under a nitrogen atmosphere. The title reaction in the presence of Cr^{III} can slowly initiate polymerization process of acrylonitrile under the experimental conditions. It indicates the generation of free radicals.

Effect of $MnSO_4$ and other factors: $MnSO_4$ (ca. $10^{-2}-10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) can itself catalyze (Fig. 3) the title reactions. The mixed catalyst, $Cr^{III} + Mn^{II}$, has been found to act antagonistically. No discernible effects of $[Na^+]$ and/or $[K^+]$ (up to 0.08 mol dm^{-3}) or of the products (up to 4.5 mol dm^{-3}) were observed. Ambient light and aerial oxygen had no effect on k_{obs} .

Fig. 3. Effect of mixed catalyst, $Cr^{III} + Mn^{II}$ on k_{obs} for the Ce^{IV} oxidation of propane-1,2-diol in aqueous H_2SO_4 media. (A) $[Mn^{II}] = 0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (B) $[Mn^{II}] = 0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} + [Cr^{III}] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (C) $[Cr^{III}] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ce^{IV}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[propane-1,2-diol]_T = 0.03 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Na^+] + [K^+] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $temp = 40^\circ$

Effect of temperature: Under the experimental conditions, the temperature range could not be extended beyond $35-50^\circ$, as below 35° the rates were too slow while above 50° the rates were too fast for kinetic study. Consequently, approximate values of the activation parameters of the composite rate constants were determined by using the

Eyring equation⁶ in the narrow span of temperature range (10°). In spite of this limitation, the activation parameters determined throw some important indications in favour of the proposed mechanism.

Mechanism of the reaction : The experimental findings stated above can be explained by considering the following reaction scheme (S = diol, i.e. HOCH₂CHROH, R = H, CH₃) :

(R = H for ethane-1,2-diol; and R = CH₃ for propane-1,2-diol)

Scheme 1

In both aqueous H₂SO₄ media⁷ and HClO₄ media⁸, Ce^{IV} has been found to oxidize the glycols through complexation followed by the C–C bond cleavage via free radical generation. For complexation with Ce^{IV}, both the OH groups are not necessarily required^{7a}. In fact, both ethane-1,2-diol and 2-methoxyethanol are oxidized^{7a} by Ce^{IV} in aqueous H₂SO₄ media via complex formation at about the same rate. For ethane-1,2-diol, though both the OH groups are available for complexation, for the methoxy derivative, only one OH group is available for complexation. Thus substitution of one hydroxy group by a methoxy group disfavours the complexation process but favours the disproportionation of the complex. Due to these two opposing effects^{8a} the overall rates of oxidation for ethane-1,2-diol and its monomethyl ether became almost equal. The kinetically active Ce^{IV} species is Ce(SO₄)₂ which has been established from the [HSO₄⁻] dependence (Fig. 2). Thus the probable structure of C₁ is (SO₄)₂Ce^{IV}–O–CH₂–CHR(OH) while C₂ (an outer-sphere complex of Cr^{III} due to the inertness⁹ of Cr^{III}, a d³-system) is (SO₄)₂Ce^{IV}–O–CH₂–CHR(OH)·Cr^{III}. But C₃ is an inner-sphere complex of Cr^{IV} which is a labile centre⁹ and it is likely to be (SO₄)₂Ce^{IV}–O–CH₂–CHR–O–Cr^{IV}. Cr^{IV} is known¹⁰ for efficient C–C bond splitting (glycol splitting) and it occurs so in the reaction step shown by eqn. (10). Here, it is worth mentioning that under the kinetic conditions, there was no spectral evidence in favour of the proposed complexes C₁, C₂ and C₃. But it does not invalidate the proposed scheme. Because of the very small steady-state concentrations of the proposed species, it is reasonable not to have any spectral evidence. It is well established⁷ that in aqueous sulfuric acid media diols undergo complexation with the Ce^{IV} centre before the slow electron transfer step, though in many cases⁷ no spectral evidence of complex formation

is available.

Under the steady-state conditions of the species C₁ and C₂, the above scheme under reasonable approximations, [Cr]_T ≈ [Cr^{III}] and [diol]_T ≈ [diol] leads to the rate equation,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = -d \ln [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt \\ = 2k_1k_2k_3/[\text{diol}]_T[\text{Cr}]_T(k_{-1}k' + k_2k_3[\text{Cr}]_T) \quad (12)$$

$$1/k_{\text{obs}} = k_{-1}k'/(2k_1k_2k_3f[\text{diol}]_T[\text{Cr}]_T) + 1/(2k_1f[\text{diol}]_T) \quad (13)$$

where *f* gives the fraction of total cerium(IV), i.e. [Ce^{IV}]_T which is kinetically active, and *k*' = *k*₋₂ + *k*₃. Eqn. (13) is in the form of eqn. (4) which is experimentally observed. Combining eqns. (2–4) and (12) we get,

$$a = 2k_1k_2k_3f, \quad b = k_{-1}k', \quad c = k_2k_3 \text{ and} \\ k_s = 2k_1k_2k_3f/[\text{Cr}]_T(k_{-1}k' + k_2k_3[\text{Cr}]_T) \quad (14)$$

To explain the origin of the catalytic power of the present system, it is reasonable to consider that formation of such Cr^{IV}-substrate inner-sphere complex (i.e. complex C₃) is expected to lower the reduction potential of Cr^{IV}/Cr^{III} system and it facilitates the electron transfer process in the *k*₃ path. Thus the generated Cr^{IV} species efficiently oxidizes the bound substrate through C–C bond splitting as shown in eqn. (10). Mn^{II} can independently act as a catalyst in the title reactions, but the mixed catalyst, Mn^{II} + Cr^{III} acts antagonistically (Fig. 3). This antagonistic activity of the mixed catalyst system indirectly supports¹¹ the involvement of Cr^{IV} in Cr^{III} catalysis. It is well established that MnSO₄ rapidly removes Cr^{IV} and thus it hinders the mixed catalyst system. Participation of the Cr^{III}/Cr^{IV} catalytic cycle in Ce^{IV} oxidation reactions in aqueous H₂SO₄ media has also been proposed^{1a,2} earlier.

From the plots of *k*_{obs} vs [diol]_T the composite rate constants (*k*_s) have been evaluated. From the plot of 1/*k*_{obs} vs 1/[Cr]_T at fixed [diol]_T, the composite rate constants, *k*_s = 2*k*₁*f* have been estimated. The values of 10³ *k*_s/s⁻¹ are : 3.83 ± 0.20 (40°), 4.90 ± 0.20 (45°), 6.53 ± 0.25 (50°) with Δ*H*[‡] ≈ 46 kJ mol⁻¹, Δ*H*[‡] ≈ -148 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for ethane-1,2-diol; and for propane-1,2-diol the values of 10² *k*_s/s⁻¹ are : 1.16 ± 0.08 (35°), 1.54 ± 0.10 (40°), 2.13 ± 0.15 (45°) with Δ*H*[‡] ≈ 49 kJ mol⁻¹, Δ*S*[‡] ≈ -125 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The more negative value of Δ*S*[‡] for ethane-1,2-diol compared to that of propane-1,2-diol supports more associative interaction in the case of ethane-1,2-diol due to less steric hindrance in complexation.

Cr^{III} is an inert centre while Ce^{IV} is a relatively more labile centre⁹. Consequently, the equilibria⁴ leading to different sulfato species of Ce^{IV} are only important to consider in the present kinetics to explain the [HSO₄⁻] dependence. Under the present conditions, the relevant equilibria^{1b,4c} are

By considering the relative magnitudes of the successive formation equilibrium constants which are in the order ^{1b,4b,4c}, $Q_1 \gg Q_2 \gg Q_3$, $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2]$ can be expressed by eqn. (18),

$$[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = \frac{Q_1 Q_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2 / [\text{H}^+]^2}{(Q_1 Q_2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2 / [\text{H}^+]^2) + (Q_1 Q_2 Q_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^3 / [\text{H}^+]^3)} \quad (18)$$

$$= [\text{Ce}^{IV}]_T / (1 + Q_3 [\text{HSO}_4^-]) = f[\text{Ce}^{IV}]_T \quad (19)$$

Using eqn.(19) in eqn. (6), the following relationship is obtained,

$$1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/m + (Q_3/m)[\text{HSO}_4^-] \quad (20)$$

Combination of the eqns. (6), (12) and (20) leads to : $n = 1$, $p = Q_3$ and

$$m = 2k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{diol}]_T [\text{Cr}]_T / (k_{-1} k' + k_2 k_3 [\text{Cr}]_T) \quad (21)$$

Eqn. (20) explains the observed $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ dependence. From the plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ (Fig. 2), the estimated $Q_3 = 4.5 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ at 45° (obtained from ethane-1,2-diol system), $= 7.2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ at 40° (obtained from propane-1,2-diol system) are in good agreement with the reported values^{1b,4c,12}. In aqueous H_2SO_4 media, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ has been identified as the kinetically active species in many cases^{1b,13}.

Experimental

Standard stock solution of Ce^{IV} was prepared by dissolving $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R., E. Merck) in aqueous H_2SO_4 media. The stock solution was kept at room temperature for more than 48 h to attain the equilibrium and was standardised by standard Mohr's solution using ferroin as indicator. The free acid content was estimated by titration with standard NaOH solution after separation of Ce^{IV} as insoluble Ce^{III} -oxalate formed by the addition of excess $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$. The Ce^{IV} solution in aqueous H_2SO_4 media is kinetically and thermodynamically fairly stable¹⁴. Ce^{III} salt solutions were prepared from the corresponding Ce^{IV} solutions after the treatment with H_2O_2 and excess of H_2O_2 was decomposed by boiling. The title diols (SRL, A.R.) free from any carbonyl compounds established by the negative test with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine were used without any further purification. The purity was also checked by density measurements. Weighed amounts of Na_2SO_4 were dissolved in equivalent quantities of H_2SO_4 to obtain the solutions of NaHSO_4 . A few experiments were carried out by using the diols obtained by distillation under reduced pressure and the results were found the same. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade of the highest purity available. Deionised

water was further purified before use by distillation from an alkaline permanganate solution.

Procedure and kinetic measurements : The quenching titrimetric technique has been discussed earlier^{1a,b}. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated from the plot of $\log_{10} [\text{Ce}^{IV}]_t$ vs time. The k_{obs} values were reproducible within the experimental error limit ($\pm 3-5\%$). Average values of at least two independent determinations of k_{obs} were taken for analysis. The reactions were studied up to at least 75% (for slower reactions) completion of the reaction. A few runs were carried out after bubbling dinitrogen through the mixture and compared with those obtained under air. However, the results were found to be the same. Ce^{IV} solutions under the present kinetic conditions are thermodynamically and kinetically stable¹⁴ and no additional precaution to exclude the diffuse-light entering the reaction solutions was taken.

All data except those for $\log_{10} [\text{Ce}^{IV}]_t$ vs t were analysed by linear least-squares methods where appropriate. Errors associated with the reported rate constants and activation parameters were estimated as usual¹⁵.

Product analysis : Under the kinetic conditions (a representative set : $[\text{Ce}^{IV}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{diol}]_T = 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cr}]_T = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) for both the title diols, in the final product solution, formaldehyde was detected by chromotropic acid test¹⁶. The colour intensity ($\lambda = 570 \text{ nm}$) due to the formaldehyde-chromotropic acid interaction in the case of ethane-1,2-diol substrate was almost double compared to the absorbance obtained for propane-1,2-diol substrate under the unidentical conditions. It indicates the glycol splitting,

(R = H for ethane-1,2-diol, and R = CH_3 for propane-1,2-diol).

That the oxidation of glycols by Ce^{IV} occurs through glycol splitting is well established^{7,8}. Acetaldehyde (one of the products in the case of propane-1,2-diol) did not respond^{16a} to the chromotropic acid test. From the stoichiometry of the reaction, it is evident that in the case of ethane-1,2-diol, double amounts of formaldehyde gets generated compared to the propane-1,2-diol system and it is also experimentally observed from the absorbance measurement.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi and Visva-Bharati for financial support.

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